

Supporting Information for:

Effect of nanocrystal shape on charge injection in CdSe/CdS dot-in-rod and rod-in-rod nano-heterostructures.

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1. Materials

1.1. Chemicals

CdO (99.99%), tributylphosphine (TBP, 99%), trioctylphosphine (TOP, 99%), TOPO (99%) and selenium powder were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Methanol (98%) and dry ethanol (99.9%, HPLC) was purchased from Thermo Scientific. Hexanes (96%) were purchased from Microchem. Hexylphosphonic acid (HPA) Tetradecylphosphonic acid (TDPA) and octadecyl phosphonic acid (ODPA) were purchased from Alfa. Octylamine (70%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. 1,8-diaminooctane (97%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Calcium hydride (97%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Tetraethylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TEAPF₆, 99+%) was purchased from Thermo Scientific and stored in Argon filled glovebox immediately upon receiving. These chemicals were used without further purification. Acetonitrile (99.5%) used in electrochemistry experiments was purchased from Central chem. Prior to the experiments, the acetonitrile was freshly purified by distillation over calcium hydride.

1.2. Synthesis of CdSe QDs

CdSe QDs cores were synthesized by a previously reported method.¹ To synthesize CdSe QD as seed, a mixture of 3.0 g TOPO, 0.280 g ODPA and 0.060 g CdO was placed in a 50 mL three-neck flask, heated to approximately 150 °C, and degassed under vacuum for about 1 hour. Once purged, the mixture was heated under nitrogen to over 300 °C until a clear, colorless cadmium-phosphonic acid complex was formed, indicating complete dissolution of CdO. At this stage, 1.5 g of TOP was introduced, and the solution was allowed to return to the desired reaction temperature for selenium precursor injection. The selenium precursor, prepared by dissolving 0.058 g of Se in 0.360 g of TOP, was injected 350 °C. Depending on the reaction time various sizes of CdSe QDs are prepared. Post-synthesis, the CdSe QDs were purified by repeated cycles of precipitation with ethanol and redispersion in hexanes, and finally stored in TOP for further use.

1.3. Synthesis of CdSe NRs

CdSe NR cores were synthesized by a previously reported method.² A standard synthesis began by combining CdO (0.2054 g, 1.6 mmol), TDPA (0.8928 g, 3.2 mmol), and TOPO (2.9028 g) in the reaction flask, then raising the temperature to 300°C under argon to fully dissolve the CdO. Once an optically clear mixture formed, the temperature was further raised to 320°C. The

solution was then cooled to room temperature and left to age in the flask for a minimum of 24 hours.

Following this aging step, a Se-TBP precursor was prepared inside an argon-filled glovebox by combining 126.34 mg Se powder (1.6 mmol) with 380 mg TBP (1.88 mmol), 1.447 g TOP, and 0.3 g toluene. This precursor was loaded into a syringe and rapidly injected into the Cd-containing flask, which had been preheated to 320°C, causing the temperature to drop to roughly 270°C. Nanorod growth was then carried out by holding the temperature within a 250–300°C window, the precise value depending on the desired rod width and aspect ratio. Growth was halted by removing the flask from the heating mantle, and the resulting nanorods were precipitated with methanol, isolated by centrifugation and decantation, and finally stored in hexane at room temperature.

1.4. Synthesis of CdSe/CdS Core shell dot in rod (DIR):

CdSe/CdS DIRs were synthesized by a previously reported method.¹ A seeded-growth strategy was used to prepare CdSe/CdS DIR. CdO (0.057 gm for DIR1 or 0.091 gm for DIR2), TOPO (3 g), ODPa (0.290 g), and, HPA (0.080 g) were first combined in the reaction flask. This mixture underwent vacuum degassing at 150°C for roughly one hour before being switched to a nitrogen atmosphere and heated to 350°C. Once the temperature had stabilized, 1.5 g of TOP was introduced into the flask.

The sulfur precursor was prepared independently by dissolving sulfur (0.120 g) in TOP (1.5 g), to which 80 nmol of CdSe seed QDs was then added. This combined Se-TOP/seed solution was rapidly injected into the CdO-containing reaction mixture held at 350°C. The injection caused a temporary temperature drop to between 280°C, with recovery occurring within a few minutes. Nanorod growth was allowed to continue for 6–8 minutes, after which the flask was removed from the heating mantle to halt the reaction. The resulting DIRs were purified by washing with ethanol and subsequently redispersed in hexane.

1.5. Synthesis of CdSe/CdS Core shell rod in rod (RIR):

CdSe/CdS rod-in-rod (RIR) nanocrystals were synthesized following the same procedure used for the dot-in-rod samples¹, with two modifications: the CdO loading was adjusted to 0.091 g, and the seed was switched from CdSe quantum dots to CdSe nanorods, using 40 nmol of NR seed in place of the 80 nmol of QD seed.

1.6. Fabrication of QD films

The purification of the crude NC solution was done by adding an equal volume of anhydrous ethanol to the NC and centrifuge. Pour off the supernatant and redispersed the precipitate in hexane/octylamine (8:1 by volume). Add anhydrous ethanol until the solution appears turbid and centrifuge. Redisperse precipitate in anhydrous hexanes. This process exchanges the heavy ligands such as TOPO, TOP, TBPA, ODPA etc by octylamine which makes easy to prepare thin film.

NC thin films were fabricated using a layer-by-layer dip-coating approach.³ ITO-coated substrates were first immersed for 30 s in a 30 μ M NC solution in hexane. The substrate was then dipped for 30 s into a stirred methanol solution containing 10 vol% 1,8-diaminooctane (DA), which acts as a bifunctional cross-linking ligand between adjacent NC layers. To remove unbound excess linker molecules, the film was subsequently immersed in neat, stirred methanol for 60 s and air-dried once more. This deposition cycle was repeated 15 times, yielding a semitransparent NC thin film.

2. Methods

2.1. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Structural and elemental characterization of the nanorods was performed using a JEOL JEM-ARM 200cF transmission electron microscope, equipped with a cold field-emission gun and spherical aberration correction, operated at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Elemental analysis was carried out using the instrument's integrated 100 mm² silicon drift detector (JED-2300, JEOL) for energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). For sample preparation, the nanorods, dispersed in n-hexane, were drop-cast onto 400-mesh Au TEM grids coated with an ultra-thin carbon/Lacey support film, and dried under gentle IR lamp heating for 10 minutes prior to imaging.

2.2. UV-VIS Absorption Spectroscopy

Electronic absorption spectra were collected using an Agilent 8453 UV-vis diode array spectrophotometer. The NCs were dispersed in hexanes and all the spectra were collected in solution form.

2.3. Photoluminescence Spectroscopy

The photoluminescence spectra were recorded using a Fluoromax 3 plus spectrofluorometer (Horiba) equipped with a Hamamatsu R13456 red-sensitive photomultiplier tube. Instrumentation/method description. The NCs were dispersed in hexanes, and all the spectra were collected in solution form.

2.4. Spectro-electrochemistry

All spectroelectrochemical (SEC) measurements were carried out in a custom-modified quartz cuvette fitted with a glass side-arm sealed with a rubber septum, configured as the electrochemical cell. The working electrode consisted of an ITO-coated glass slide (Delta Technologies, sheet resistance 8–12 Ω) supporting the NC thin film, with a Pt wire serving as the counter electrode and an Ag wire as the pseudo-reference electrode; all three electrodes were connected to a CH Instruments potentiostat. Absorption spectra during SEC experiments were recorded using an Agilent 8453 UV-vis diode-array spectrophotometer.

Acetonitrile was used as the solvent and TEAPF₆ as the supporting electrolyte throughout all experiments. The acetonitrile was freshly distilled over calcium hydride under argon prior to use. To prepare the electrolyte solution, 275 mg (1 mmol) of TEAPF₆ was weighed inside an argon-filled glovebox and transferred to a round-bottom flask, which was then sealed with a

rubber septum and removed from the glovebox. Using a gas-tight syringe, 10 mL of the freshly distilled acetonitrile was added to the flask, and the resulting solution was degassed by argon bubbling for 20 min to remove residual dissolved oxygen. This electrolyte solution was then transferred into the electrochemical cell through the septum using a gas-tight syringe, followed by an additional 5–10 min of argon purging. A slight positive argon overpressure was maintained within the cell throughout the duration of each experiment.

2.5. Method to calculate average number of injected electron ($\langle N_{inj} \rangle$)

The band-edge absorbance, corresponding to the $1S_e$ transitions in Cd-chalcogenide QDs, is directly proportional to the occupancy of the $1S_e$ conduction band state. This relationship is captured by the expression $\langle N_{inj} \rangle = g(\Delta A/A_0)$, where $\langle N_{inj} \rangle$ denotes the average number of electrons populating the state of interest, ΔA is the change in absorbance upon charging, A_0 is the absorbance of the neutral (uncharged) film, and g is the degeneracy of the electronic level equal to 2 for the $1S_e$ conduction band state in Cd-chalcogenide nanocrystals, reflecting its twofold spin degeneracy.

3. Results

3.1. TEM of CdSe QD1, CdSe/CdS DIR1 and CdSe/CdS DIR2

Figure S1. TEM of CdSe QD1 (a) CdSe/CdS DIR1 (b) CdSe/CdS DIR2 (c). EDX mapping of CdSe/CdS DIR1. In the color element mapping Cd, Se, and S are indicated by yellow (d), dark orange (e), and light orange (f) colors, respectively. Size distribution of CdSe QD1 with diameter 3.64 ± 0.24 nm (g). Size distribution of CdSe/CdS DIR1 with length 17.6 ± 1.57 (h) and width 4.34 ± 0.41 nm (i). Size distribution of CdSe/CdS DIR2 with length 48.36 ± 4.25 (j) and width 5.35 ± 0.69 nm (k).

3.2. TEM of CdSe NR1 and CdSe/CdS RIR1

Figure S2. TEM of CdSe NR1 (a) and CdSe/CdS RIR1 (b). Size distribution of CdSe NR1 with length 14.42 ± 2.38 nm (c) and width 3.75 ± 0.51 nm (d). Size distribution of CdSe/CdS RIR1 with length 41.76 ± 3.45 (e) and width 5.29 ± 0.78 nm (f).

3.3. TEM of CdSe QD2 and CdSe/CdS DIR3

Figure S3. TEM of CdSe QD2 (a) and CdSe/CdS DIR3 (b). Size distribution of CdSe QD2 with diameter 7.45 ± 0.95 nm (c). Size distribution of CdSe/CdS RIR1 with length 8.17 ± 1.15 nm (d) and width 22.02 ± 1.79 nm (e).

3.4 TEM of CdSe NR2 and CdSe/CdS RIR2

Figure S4. TEM of CdSe NR2 (a) and CdSe/CdS RIR2 (b). Size distribution of CdSe NR2 with length 20.52 ± 2.18 nm (c) and width 5.55 ± 0.52 nm (d). Size distribution of CdSe/CdS RIR2 with length 126.47 ± 18.98 nm (e) and width 6.83 ± 1.04 nm (f).

3.5 Absorption Spectra of CdSe QD, CdSe NR, CdSe DIR and CdSe RIR

Figure S5. Steady-state UV vis absorption spectra of the spherical core, nanorod core, and corresponding core-shell heterostructure samples used in this study: (a) QD1 (black), DIR1 (red), and DIR2 (blue); (b) NR1 (black) and RIR1 (red); (c) QD2 (black) and DIR3 (red); (d) NR2 (black) and RIR2 (red). In each panel, the progressive red-shift and emergence of additional excitonic features upon CdS shelling reflect increasing shell thickness and the corresponding delocalization of the conduction band electron wavefunction into the shell.

3.6 PL spectra of CdSe QD, CdSe NR, CdSe DIR and CdSe RIR

Figure S5. Emission spectra of the NCs used in this study. Left column (a, c, e, g): PL spectra recorded under 490 nm excitation, reflecting the relative emission intensity of each sample. Right column (b, d, f, h): corresponding normalized PL spectra, facilitating direct comparison of emission peak positions. Panels (a, b): QD1 (black), DIR1 (red), and DIR2 (blue). Panels (c, d): NR1 (black) and RIR1 (red). Panels (e, f): QD2 (black) and DIR3 (red). Panels (g, h): NR2 (black) and RIR2 (red).

3.6 Quantitation of the number of injected charges

Figure S7. Average number of injected electrons per nanocrystal, $\langle N_{inj} \rangle$, calculated from the expression $\langle N_{inj} \rangle = g(\Delta A/A_0)$, plotted as a function of applied potential (vs. Ag) for all sample series studied. (a) QD1 (black), DIR1 core (red), DIR1 shell (blue), DIR2 core (orange), and DIR2 shell (purple). (b) NR1 (black), RIR1 core (red), and RIR1 shell (blue). (c) QD2 (black), DIR3 core (red), and DIR3 shell (blue). (d) NR2 (black), RIR2 core (red), and RIR2 shell (blue).

3.7 Differential relative bleach of QD1, DIR1 and DIR2

Figure S8. Differential relative bleach, defined as $[(1/A_0) \cdot \Delta(\Delta A/A)]$, plotted as a function of applied potential for (a) QD1, (b, c) DIR1 monitored at the CdSe core and CdS shell bleach maxima, respectively, and (d, e) DIR2 monitored at the CdSe core and CdS shell bleach maxima, respectively.

3.8 Differential relative bleach of NR1 and RIR1

Figure S9. Differential relative bleach, defined as $[(1/A_0) \cdot \Delta(\Delta A/A)]$, plotted as a function of applied potential for (a) NR1, (b, c) RIR1 monitored at the CdSe core and CdS shell at band edge, respectively.

3.9 Differential relative bleach of QD2 and DIR3

Figure S10. Differential relative bleach, defined as $[(1/A_0) \cdot \Delta(\Delta A/A)]$, plotted as a function of applied potential for (a) QD2, (b, c) DIR3 monitored at the CdSe core and CdS shell bleach maxima, respectively.

3.10 Differential relative bleach of NR2 and RIR3

Figure S11. Differential relative bleach, defined as $[(1/A_0) \cdot \Delta(\Delta A/A)]$, plotted as a function of applied potential for (a) NR1, (b, c) RIR1 monitored at the CdSe core and CdS shell bleach maxima, respectively.

4. References

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